

Single- And Repeated-Dose Inhalation Toxicity of Medicinal Cigarettes with Antitussive and Expectorants in ICR Mice

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ABSTRACT

Antitussives suppress coughing, possibly by reducing brain cough center activity, while expectorants thin mucus to help loosen congestion and clear airways. Inhaling antitussives and expectorants, involving using inhaled vapors or aerosolized medications to manage cough and mucus, allow for direct inhalation into the respiratory tract to provide faster relief. However, the reported adverse effects raised question as to whether inhaling antitussives and expectorants directly can pose risks. Therefore, the present study aimed to assess the toxicological profile of medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants, though single- and repeated-dose toxicity test. Male and female ICR mice were received by whole-body inhalation at target mainstream smoke concentrations of 95 mg/m³ total particulate matter (TPM) of medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants in the single-dose toxicity test. In the repeated-dose toxicity study, no mortality or behavioral signs of toxicity were observed, indicating the LD₅₀ was higher than 95 mg/m³ in the exposure period and the following 2 weeks observation period. In the repeated-dose inhalation toxicity study, the potential toxic effects of medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants were examined using ICR mice exposed for 4 weeks, by whole-body inhalation at target mainstream smoke concentrations of 15.7, 27.9 and 47.5 mg/m³ TPM, while control rats were exposed to filtered air. There was no significant difference observed in the body weights, feed consumption, relative organ weights, haematological, prothrombin and partial thromboplastin time, and serum biochemical findings. The histopathologic examination also did not show any differences in vital organs. These data suggested that medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants used in this study did not produce any marked repeated-dose toxic effects up to a maximum concentration of 47.5 mg/m³ TPM.

Keywords: Single- and repeated-dose toxicity; whole-body inhalation; Medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants; Mice

INTRODUCTION

Cough is defined as a forced expulsive maneuver, usually against a closed glottis which is associated with a characteristic sound [1]. Cough is a protective physiological reflex deputed to clear secretions from the airways or remove inhaled materials. Cough can be also the result of several respiratory tract disorders which may require drug treatment for its relief. Coughing is related to several respiratory diseases such as asthma, bronchitis, pneumonia, etc [2-4]. They originate in afferent nervous systems that detect and signal real or impending threats to the

organism [2-4]. Despite the presence of a definitive diagnosis, managing cough can prove challenging and may result in an impaired quality of life [5-7].

There are many types of drugs that are used to suppress cough and are often prescribed in combination. A lot of medicines have been used over the past centuries as cough suppressants or antitussives [8-10]. Antitussives and expectorants are two different classes of medications. But these two medications work differently and have different uses. Antitussives suppress cough reflexes, aiding in dry cough relief. Expectorants enhance the projection of respiratory tract fluid and thus facilitate the mobilization and discharge of bronchial secretions [8-10].

Antitussives and expectorants can be inhaled, but the primary method for their administration is typically through oral medications. Inhaled antitussives and expectorants are not common, but specific options like ipratropium bromide, which has shown some cough suppression in bronchitis, are used [11]. Medicinal cigarette is a cigarette that usually does not contain any tobacco or nicotine, instead being composed of a mixture, instead being composed of a mixture of drug or various medicinal herb [12].

The aim of present study was to evaluate toxic effects of medicinal cigarette that have antitussives and expectorants effects based on the safety testing guidelines established by the Korea Food and Drug Administration using a whole-body inhalation system. Thus, the animals were exposed to medicinal cigarette that have antitussives and expectorants effects for two (single-dose) and four (repeated-dose) consecutive weeks except for the control group that received high efficiency particulate air (HEPA)-filtered fresh air. The current study described a single- and repeated-dose toxicity study, in order to evaluate the toxicological safety of medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants for the assessment of potential adverse health effects to human.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test substance

Medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants was prepared by the 3R-Care Co., Ltd in Seoul, Korea. It was constructed using conventional 100 mm design with cellulose acetate filters.

Smoking equipment and inhalation chamber

For the inhalation toxicity evaluation, a cigarette smoke generator (Dustrubo, Korea), internationally certified, was used to simulate conditions similar to human smoking. The generator inhaled once per minute, drawing 35 cc of smoke over a two-second duration with a velocity of 25 cm per second at the tip of the filter (32 mm from the tip). The mainstream and sidestream smoke were simultaneously directed into an inhalation chamber for exposure.

A 0.5 m³ whole-body inhalation exposure chamber was used, with an air turnover of 15 cycles per hour. Smoke uniformity within the chamber was ensured by sampling from 12 different locations and using a recirculation system. After exposure, the air was filtered through activated carbon, scrubbers, and HEPA filters before being released into the environment.

CO measure and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of total particulate matters (TPMs) /MS) analysis of total particulate

Carbon monoxide (CO) and respiratory solid particles were measured in the inhalation chambers using a CO gas analyzer (Model MSA, USA) and personal air samplers (Model MSA, USA). CO levels were measured five times over the study period at 1 hour intervals, and the average and error were calculated. Respiratory particles were collected according to NIOSH guidelines five times, and their weight was measured.

The amount of Total particulate matter (TPM) was measured by weighing the filter before and after the collection of TPMs. For the measurement of several representative polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) concentrations in medicinal cigarette with antitussive and

expectorants, TPMs were extracted from the nitrocellulose membrane using 20 mL of n-hexane by employing the sonic extraction method. The n-hexane extract was reextracted with 20 mL of ethyl acetate and evaporated. An Hewlett-Packard Model 5890A gas chromatograph was operated in conjunction with a VG Analytical Model 70-SE mass spectrometer and a VG-11-250J mass data system. An ultra-2 column containing cross-linked 5% phenylmethylsilicon (25 m× 0.2 mm I.D.× 0.33 mm film thickness) was used. Column temperature was programmed at 15 °C/min from 230 to 310 °C (injection temperature, 280 °C; transfer line temperature, 280 °C; helium flow-rate, 0.7 mL/min).

Animals, housing conditions and diet

The experimental animals used were SPF (Specific Pathogen-Free) ICR mice, sourced from SAMTAKO Inc. (Osan, Korea) at 6 weeks of age. After acclimating the mice in the laboratory for approximately one week, healthy animals were selected. The animals were housed in groups of five per cage under controlled conditions (temperature: 23 ± 3 °C, humidity: $50 \pm 10\%$, ventilation: 10-12 air changes per hour, light/dark cycle: 12 hours, light intensity: 150-160 Lux) throughout the study period. Each cage was tagged with the test number, animal ID, and dose. Animals were provided with standard laboratory chow and tap water ad libitum. The animal experiments were conducted following the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals [13] and approved by Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee, Jeju National University (Jeju, Korea) for Animal ethics.

Single-dose toxicity test

Single-dose toxicity tests for medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants were performed using the method described before [14].

The selected dose of the test substance was mixed with air and injected into the chamber, with an airflow rate set to ensure 15 air changes per hour. Oxygen levels were maintained at 19%, temperature at 22 ± 3 °C, and humidity between 30-70%. The chamber volume occupied by the animals was restricted to less than 5% of the total chamber volume. The exposure duration was six hours after achieving a uniform concentration of the test substance.

Clinical observations were made daily for 14 days, noting any changes in general condition, signs of intoxication, mortality, and symptoms related to the administration of the test substance. Observations included monitoring the skin, fur, eyes, mucous membranes, respiratory, circulatory, autonomic, and central nervous systems, motor activity, behavior, tremors, convulsions, salivation, diarrhea, lethargy, sleep, and coma.

Body weights were measured prior to the test and at the end of the study. Body weight was also measured weekly during the test period.

After the study ended (on day 14), all surviving mice were estimated the medium single-dose toxicity values (LD_{50}) before necropsy [15], and a detailed visual inspection was performed post-mortem.

Repeated-dose toxicity test

The selected doses were mixed with air and injected into the chamber, with airflow set to 15 changes per hour. Oxygen levels were maintained at 19%, temperature at 22 ± 3 °C, and humidity at 30-70%. The exposure was conducted for 6 hours per day, 5 days per week, for 4 weeks.

Clinical observations were conducted daily to monitor the health status of all animals and look for any signs of toxicity or mortality.

Body weight and food intake were measured weekly for all animals during the study period, with records taken before dosing and at necropsy.

Blood was collected from the ophthalmic vein and abdominal aorta after fasting for 24 hours prior to necropsy. Hematological parameters, including hematocrit, red blood cell count (RBC), white blood cell count (WBC), differential WBC count, and coagulation time (prothrombin

time (PT) and partial thromboplastin time (PTT)), were analyzed using an automatic blood analyzer.

After necropsy, blood samples were processed for biochemical analysis. Serum was analyzed for total protein, albumin, bilirubin, liver enzymes (AST, ALT), glucose, creatinine, blood urea nitrogen, electrolytes (calcium, phosphorus, chloride, sodium), and other markers.

Organ weights were measured, and visual inspection for any abnormalities in organs such as the liver, lungs, kidneys, adrenal glands, gonads, heart, brain, spleen, bladder, and others was performed.

After the 4-week exposure, histopathological examinations were carried out on the preserved organs and tissues. The organs listed above were harvested and fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 48 h. The fixed organs were processed for paraffin embedding. Paraffin Sections (5 mm thick) were cut using a standard microtome, processed with the alcohol: xylene series, stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H & E) and observed by light microscopy..

Statistical analysis

Statistical comparisons between groups were conducted using one-way ANOVA, followed by Student's t-test ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$) for significant differences. As no mortality occurred during the study, the determination of the LD₅₀ value was not applicable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Animal model toxicity tests were carried out to assess the safety and to determine the optimal dose of a drug for disease treatment [16]. Toxicological studies in animals, rodents as well as non-rodents are extremely important to determine the protection and effectiveness of biological material, according to OECD guidelines.

CO measure and GC-MS analysis of TPMs /

CO levels in the exposure chamber were 6.6 ± 0.74 ppm, 11.0 ± 1.36 ppm, and 18.2 ± 0.77 ppm for the low (5 cigarettes), medium (10 cigarettes), and high (20 cigarettes) dose groups, respectively, while the control group showed no CO. Respiratory particle measurements were 15.7 ± 0.98 mg/m³, 27.9 ± 1.14 mg/m³ and 47.5 ± 0.41 mg/m³ for the low, medium, and high dose groups, respectively.

In the repeated-dose toxicity study, no PAHs were detected in the low (2 samples), medium (4 samples), or high (3 samples) dose of the test substances. However, several similar peaks were observed. Most of the samples extracted with n-hexane showed peaks around the retention time (13.934 minutes) similar to that of 9-nitroanthracene. In the high-concentration repeated dose toxicity samples, peaks were observed around the retention time (19.861 minutes) of perylene, although the mass pattern was different from that of the standard reference. In the samples extracted with ethyl acetate, peaks were observed around the retention time (4.959 minutes) of naphthalene. However, no other substances were recovered from the fortified sample, and similar-sized peaks were also observed in the blank filter, suggesting that these peaks were not derived from the test samples (data not shown).

Single-dose toxicity test

Single-dose toxicity assessments are performed to evaluate the immediate toxic properties of the extract when given in a single dose in rodents by individually assessing mortality, toxicity, physiological, behavioral, neurological and gross histological changes [17].

No mortality occurred during the exposure period in any dose group, and no clinical symptoms were observed (data not shown). No significant body weight changes were also observed between the control and treatment groups (Table 1). No abnormal findings were observed during necropsy in either the control or treatment groups.

Repeated-dose toxicity test

The repeated-dose toxicity tests are intended to evaluate the lethal effects of test material when given repeatedly in rodents for 28 days by evaluating body weights, blood and biochemical parameters, histological and pathological changes [18].

No mortality occurred during the study in any group, and no symptoms of toxicity were observed.

No significant differences in food intake were observed between the control and treatment groups (Table 2).

Hematological parameters played a vital role in the evaluation of toxicity [19]. The serum biochemical parameters play a significant role as biomarkers in repeated-dose toxicological evaluation [20]. No significant changes were observed in hematological or biochemical tests between the control and treatment groups (Tables 3-5).

Compared with the control group, there were no significant differences in bodyweight (Figure 1) before sacrifice, liver, kidney, spleen and testis weight as well as corresponding organ to bodyweight ratio among treatment groups (data not shown).

No pathological changes were observed in the histopathological examination of organs in any group.

CONCLUSION

In brief, these data suggested that medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants did not produce any marked repeated-dose toxic effects up to a maximum concentration of 47.5 mg/m³ TPM. In addition, the result of the single-dose toxicity test was also negative. These data provided supportive evidence for the safety of medicinal cigarette with antitussive and expectorants that may be used to manage coughs.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there is no competing interest.

REFERENCES

1. Murgia V, Manti S, Licari A, Filippo M (2020) Upper respiratory tract infection-associated acute cough and the urge to cough: new insights for clinical practice. *Pediatric Allergy, Immunology, and Pulmonology* 33(1), 3-11. DOI:10.1089/ped.2019.1135.
2. Kang SY, Won HK, Lee SM, Kwon JW, Kim MH, Jo EJ, Lee SE, Kim SH, Chang YS, Lee SP, Lee BJ, Cho SH, Bitting SS, Song WJ (2019) Impact of cough and unmet needs in chronic cough: a survey of patients in Korea. *Lung* 197, 635-639. DOI: 10.1007/s00408-019-00258-9.
3. Morice AH, McGarvey L, Pavord I (2006) Recommendations for the management of cough in adults. *Thorax* 61 Suppl 1, 1-24. DOI: 10.1136/thx.2006.065144.
4. Song WJ, Chang YS, Faruqi S, Kim JY, Kang MG, Kim S, Jo EJ, Kim MH, Plevkova, Park HW, Cho SH, Morice AH (2015) The global epidemiology of chronic cough in adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Respiratory Journal* 45, 1479-1481. DOI: 10.1183/09031936.00218714.
5. Birring SS, Prudon B, Carr AJ, Singh S, Morgan MD, Pavord I (2003). Development of a symptom specific health status measure for patients with chronic cough: Leicester Cough Questionnaire (LCQ). *Thorax* 58, 339-343. DOI: 10.1136/thorax.58.4.339.
6. French CT, Irwin RS, Fletcher KE, Adams TM (2002) Evaluation of a cough-specific quality-of-life questionnaire. *Chest* 121, 1123-1131. DOI: 10.1378/chest.121.4.1123.
7. Won HK, Lee JH, An J, Sohn KH, Kang MG, Kang SY, Morice AH, Cho SH, Song WJ (2020) Impact of chronic cough on health-related quality of life in the Korean adult general population: The Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2010-2016. *Allergy Asthma & Immunology Resesarch* 12, 964-79. DOI: 10.4168/aaair.2020.12.6.964.
8. Hughes DTD (1978) Today's treatment, disease of the respiratory system cough suppressants, expectorant and mucolytics. *British Medical Journal* 1, 1202-1203. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.1.6121.1202.
9. Bennett PN, Brown MJ (2003) *Clinical pharmacology*, 9th ed., Elsevier, a division of Reed, Churchill Livingstone Indian Pvt Ltd., Noida, pp. 212.

10. Gairola S, Gupta V, Basal P, Singh R, Maithani M (2010) Herbal antitussives and expectorants. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research* 5(2), 5-9. DOI: 10.1177/1934578X19850354.
11. Bolser DC (2006) Cough suppressant and pharmacologic protussive therapy. *Chest* 129, 238S-249S. DOI: 10.1378/chest.129.1_suppl.238S.
12. Jadhao AS, Shaikh FT, Sirsat DR (2024) Synthesis and characterization of medicinal cigarette, conference: n 'Synergy in Science: Integrating Life and Chemical Sciences XIII(VIII).
13. Icjihara G, Katsumata Y, Moriyama H, Kitakata H, Hirai A, Momoi M, Ko S, Shinya Y, Kinouchi K, Ko-bayashi E, Sano M (2021) Pharmacokinetics of hydrogen after ingesting a hydrogen-rich solution: A study in pigs. *Heliyon* 7(11), e08359. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08359.
14. Kim MY (2022) Cytotoxicity and acute toxicity evaluation of hydrogen-rich *Gynostemma pentaphyllum* Makino distillate. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science* 14(3), 771-776. DOI: 10.31018/jans.v14i3.3569.
15. Shafaei A, Esmaili K, Farsi E, Aisha AF, Abul Majid AM, Ismail Z (2015) Genotoxicity, acute and subchronic toxicity studies of nano liposomes of *Orthosiphon stamineus* ethanolic extract in Sprague Dawley rats. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 15, 360. DOI: 10.1186/s12906-015-0885-z
16. Saganuwan SA (2017). Toxicity studies of drugs and chemicals in animals: An overview. *Bulgarian Journal of Veterinary Medicine* 20(4), 291-318. DOI: 10.15547/bjvm.983.
17. Earnest OE, Ihekwereme CP, Ildigwe EE (2018) Advances in acute toxicity testing: strengths, weaknesses and regulatory acceptance. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology* 11(1), 5-12. DOI: 10.2478/intox-2018-0001.
18. Rania HA, Basha WA, Khalil WF (2019) Subacute toxicity of *Nerium oleander* ethanolic extract in mice. *Toxicological Research* 35(3), 233-239. DOI: 10.5487/TR.2019.35.3.233.
19. Raina P, Chandrasekaran CV, Deepak M, Aggarwal A, Ruchika KG (2015) Evaluation of sub-acute toxicity of methanolic/aqueous preparation of aerial parts of *O. sanctum* in Wistar rats: Clinical, haematological, biochemical and histopathological studies. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 175:509-517. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2015.10.015.
20. Kianoush S, Balali-Mood M, Mousavi SR, Shakeri MT, Dadpour B, Moradi V, Sadeghi M (2013) Clinical, toxicological, biochemical and hematologic parameters in lead exposed workers of a car battery industry. *Iranian Journal of Medical Science* 38(1), 30-37. DOI: 10.30476/ijms.2013.39510.

Table 1. Body weights of the mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 14 days

Gender	Group	Days after administration				
		0	4	7	10	14
Male	Control	31.2±1.30	34.6±1.95	34.0±2.00	35.2±2.28	35.6±1.52
	95 mg/m ³	30.8±0.39	34.2±2.27	33.8±1.92	35.0±2.00	35.4±1.14
Female	Control	26.8±2.39	29.4±2.51	29.6±1.52	29.8±0.84	30.0±2.12
	95 mg/m ³	26.0±1.22	29.6±2.30	29.6±1.14	29.6±1.14	30.4±2.51

Data are mean ± S.D. (n=10)

Table 2. Food consumption of the mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 4 weeks (unit: g)

Gender	Group	Weeks after treatment			
		1	2	3	4
Male	Control	28.5±0.07	31.0±0.71	33.3±0.49	34.5±0.64
	15.7 mg/m ³	27.5±0.35	29.6±0.28	33.5±1.34	33.5±1.27
	27.9 mg/m ³	28.1±0.07	30.0±0.71	32.8±1.70	33.1±3.32
Female	47.5 mg/m ³	28.8±0.42	30.8±0.57	33.0±1.41	33.8±0.14
	Control	23.0±0.71	24.0±1.41	26.4±0.57	27.2±0.28
	15.7 mg/m ³	23.5±0.35	25.5±1.06	26.9±0.35	26.6±0.14

	27.9 mg/m ³	24.0±1.41	24.1±0.49	26.2±0.42	26.3±0.35
	47.5 mg/m ³	23.6±0.57	23.5±1.06	25.9±0.21	26.2±0.57

Data are mean ± S.D. (n=10)

Table 3. Hematological findings of the mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 4 weeks

Gender	Male				Female			
	Control	15.7 mg/m ³	27.9 mg/m ³	47.5 mg/m ³	Control	15.7 mg/m ³	27.9 mg/m ³	47.5 mg/m ³
WBC (×10 ³ /μℓ)	3.5±0.85	3.4±0.98	3.4±1.16	3.4±1.12	3.3±0.75	3.4±0.53	3.4±0.39	3.3±0.47
NE (×10 ³ /μℓ)	0.7±0.19	0.7±0.22	0.7±0.10	0.7±0.14	0.7±0.15	0.7±0.07	0.8±0.08	0.8±0.11
LY (×10 ³ /μℓ)	2.0±0.87	2.0±0.89	2.0±0.82	2.1±1.00	2.1±1.48	2.2±0.57	2.2±0.61	2.1±0.36
MO (×10 ³ /μℓ)	0.3±0.14	0.3±0.08	0.3±0.11	0.3±0.13	0.3±0.08	0.3±0.10	0.3±0.15	0.3±0.13
EO (×10 ³ /μℓ)	0.06±0.03	0.06±0.03	0.07±0.02	0.06±0.04	0.1±0.02	0.1±0.02	0.1±0.03	0.1±0.02
BA (×10 ³ /μℓ)	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.00	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.01	0.01±0.01
NE (%)	47.1±10.80	47.1±17.98	50.1±23.91	50.6±23.35	46.8±12.13	45.5±7.64	48.5±14.85	46.6±8.70
LY (%)	63.3±11.10	65.1±12.00	62.0±14.44	62.4±20.24	62.8±15.91	66.0±7.14	64.5±7.82	65.4±3.56
MO (%)	9.1±3.86	9.1±3.96	9.0±8.13	9.7±8.88	8.8±2.63	9.1±3.71	8.3±3.27	8.7±3.62
EO (%)	2.4±0.55	2.3±0.33	2.5±1.37	2.2±1.58	2.4±0.78	2.4±0.40	2.5±0.90	2.3±0.64
BA (%)	0.4±0.18	0.4±0.29	0.4±0.19	0.4±0.16	0.4±0.25	0.4±0.18	0.4±0.11	0.4±0.14
RBC (×10 ³ /μℓ)	10.1±3.22	10.3±1.50	10.1±1.25	10.6±2.30	9.7±2.43	9.7±0.95	9.8±1.25	9.6±0.87
HCT(50.8±14.	49.8±12.04	50.8±4.71	51.4±15.54	55.9±13.	54.8±4.98	56.0±3.84	56.3±6.24

(%)	52				50			
PLT ($\times 10^3/\mu\ell$)	604.0 \pm 20.89	603.7 \pm 16.4	595.8 \pm 48.20	608.9 \pm 14.34	574.4 \pm 12.84	573.5 \pm 7.04	572.1 \pm 9.08	572.9 \pm 14.19

Data are mean \pm S.D. (n=10), WBC: white blood cell, NE: neutrophil, LY: Lymphocyte, MO: Monocyte, EO: Eosinophil, BA: Basophil, RBC: red blood cell, HCT: hematocrit, PLT: platelet

Table 4. Prothrombin time and partial thromboplastin time of the mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 4 weeks (unit: sec)

Gender		Control	15.7 mg/m ³	27.9 mg/m ³	47.5 mg/m ³
Male	PTT	29.52 \pm 2.85	30.79 \pm 1.95	30.74 \pm 3.57	30.28 \pm 2.53
	PT	19.89 \pm 1.53	20.92 \pm 2.95	20.66 \pm 1.80	20.12 \pm 2.80
Female	PTT	28.37 \pm 5.11	28.86 \pm 3.55	31.53 \pm 7.36	29.60 \pm 3.66
	PT	19.44 \pm 2.51	18.82 \pm 2.04	19.58 \pm 3.05	20.66 \pm 5.07

Data are mean \pm S.D. (n=10)

Table 5. Biochemical findings of the mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 4 weeks

Gender	Male				Female			
	Control	15.7 mg/m ³	27.9 mg/m ³	47.5 mg/m ³	Control	15.7 mg/m ³	27.9 mg/m ³	47.5 mg/m ³
TPROT (g/dl)	47.8 \pm 5.19	47.3 \pm 7.04	48.8 \pm 5.49	48.1 \pm 3.81	53.7 \pm 3.59	52.7 \pm 3.16	52.6 \pm 3.75	53.5 \pm 2.32
ALB (U/L)	3.9 \pm 0.53	3.7 \pm 0.37	3.9 \pm 0.41	3.9 \pm 0.56	4.1 \pm 0.41	4.0 \pm 0.44	4.0 \pm 0.56	4.1 \pm 0.21
TBILI (mg/dl)	0.4 \pm 0.05	0.4 \pm 0.02	0.4 \pm 0.04	0.4 \pm 0.04	0.4 \pm 0.04	0.4 \pm 0.03	0.4 \pm 0.04	0.4 \pm 0.03
AST (u/l)	42.8 \pm 3.42	42.4 \pm 4.65	41.9 \pm 5.12	42.7 \pm 1.76	43.4 \pm 3.08	41.3 \pm 5.88	42.4 \pm 4.64	42.6 \pm 4.25
ALT (u/l)	43.7 \pm 4.83	41.5 \pm 4.26	41.7 \pm 3.36	42.7 \pm 7.63	43.5 \pm 6.53	42.2 \pm 4.17	41.7 \pm 4.91	42.9 \pm 5.49
GLU (mg/dl)	59.6 \pm 5.99	60.9 \pm 4.90	60.1 \pm 4.67	61.8 \pm 4.29	60.0 \pm 19.06	61.2 \pm 13.77	60.1 \pm 8.71	62.2 \pm 7.08
CREAT (mg/dl)	0.9 \pm 0.15	0.9 \pm 0.16	0.9 \pm 0.19	0.9 \pm 0.20	0.8 \pm 0.33	0.8 \pm 0.14	0.8 \pm 0.10	0.8 \pm 0.29
BUN (mg/dl)	13.9 \pm 1.96	13.8 \pm 1.39	14.1 \pm 1.90	13.9 \pm 1.37	13.9 \pm 1.60	13.9 \pm 1.20	13.8 \pm 1.55	13.9 \pm 0.99
Na (mEq/L)	143.3 \pm 5.05	145.2 \pm 1.07	143.7 \pm 6.30	142.4 \pm 7.23	141.4 \pm 7.40	141.1 \pm 5.58	143.1 \pm 1.23	143.2 \pm 5.16
Ca (mg/dl)	6.0 \pm 0.93	6.1 \pm 0.76	6.0 \pm 1.08	6.0 \pm 0.60	5.9 \pm 1.26	5.9 \pm 1.29	5.9 \pm 0.65	6.0 \pm 1.22

P (mg/dl)	4.6±0.55	4.5±0.93	4.6±0.71	4.6±1.01	4.0±1.01	4.3±1.21	4.0±1.05	3.9±0.88
Cl (mEq/L)	115.8±9.26	112.2±8.09	111.9±5.99	107.8±6.39	108.0±6.16	107.0±5.93	108.3±4.03	109.9±5.67

Data are mean ± S.D. (n=10). TPROT: total protein, ALB: albumin, TBILI: total bilirubin, AST: aspartate aminotransferase, ALT: alanine aminotransferase, GLU: glucose, CREAT: creatinine, BUN: blood urea nitrogen, NA: sodium, CA: calcium, P: phosphorus, CL: chloride.

Figure 1. Body weight changes of male (A) and female (B) ICR mice treated with medicinal cigarettes with antitussive and expectorants for 4 weeks. Each point represents the Data are mean ± S.D. (n=10). ○: Control; □: 15.7 mg/m³; ▲: 27.9 mg/m³; ▽: 47.5 mg/m³. No significant differences were found between group; Student's t-test.